

DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE POTENTIAL OF CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: In this article, the building materials industry in our country Socio-economic nature and construction of innovative potential of enterprises materials industry, affecting the innovation potential of enterprises, internal and analysis of external factors is presented. Also building materials. The main factors of the development of the innovative potential of the industry are a number of world. The results of scientific research of scientists are analyzed and developed by the author developed models are presented.

Key words: building materials, innovative potential, construction, industry, factors.

Further deepening of economic reforms in the building materials industry and rapid development of the network, new modern building materials, constructions and increasing the production of goods and expanding its types, personnel implementation of nationwide programs for the development of training, school education and housing construction taking into account the increase in the domestic market's demand for construction materials ensuring satisfaction, as well as increasing the export potential of economic reforms is becoming one of the priority tasks. The construction industry is part of the economy of Uzbekistan stable growth rates among the sectors of the national economy as a priority is one of the fields of note.

The fact that increasing the innovative potential of the construction materials industry is considered as an important factor of the socio-economic development of the country is a factor of great results. According to Uzsanoatkurilishbank, one of the institutions responsible for this, in the first half of this year, the value is 995 mln. 181 dollar projects were financed and 87 projects were launched.

In the decree of the President of June 9, 2021 "On additional measures to increase the industrial potential of the regions", all the organizational and practical mechanisms of raising the construction materials production sector to a new level were determined.

A management system and targeted strategy aimed at increasing the economic efficiency of enterprises, strengthening the production of competitive and exportable products was developed.

As of July 1 of this year, as of July 1 of this year, 14.4 trillion. 1.9 trillion soums of construction materials were produced compared to last year. increased to soum. Of this, 459 billion Soum products were delivered to consumers within the framework of the localization program, and the target indicators for the development of the network for this year were more than fulfilled. 560 mln. the absorption of foreign and domestic investments in the amount of dollars is of particular importance.

It should be noted that in 2022, 420 investment projects worth 1.8 billion dollars (including project initiators' own funds - 642 million dollars, bank loans - 473 million dollars,

foreign investments - 708 million dollars) will be implemented in the sector. increase, 27.6 trillion by network enterprises. production of products worth 15,533 soums and creation of 15,533 new jobs is planned.

Accordingly, to date, together with commercial banks, the value is 995 mln. (own funds - 403 million dollars, bank loan - 422 million dollars, foreign investments - 170 million dollars) 181 projects were financed and 87 projects were launched¹

Sustainable innovative development system of building materials industry means across time and space at all levels and divisions of industry wide, which ensures a continuous and effective flow of the innovation process a large-scale mechanism is understood. The Ministry of Construction and Housing and Communal Economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the regulatory documents on the establishment of this Ministry of the country modern needs of the national economy and society of the construction complex and intended to ensure operation in accordance with requirements. This state structure is essentially an organizational-production cluster. And this is separate companies and a mutually complementary and strengthening competitor of the cluster as a whole advantages. In other words, a cluster, with proper processing, is unique to systems it is possible to ensure a synergistic effect by realizing the characteristic of integrity will give.

It can be seen that the Republic of Uzbekistan is a construction and housing and communal sector the Ministry of Economy to adequately develop the construction industry at the national level in conditions aimed at providing, subordinate structures and economic operator from market methods to support initiatives of entities must coordinate use with administrative resources.

In creating a system of sustainable innovative development of the construction industry this is what is aimed at and the ultimate goal. In the creation of the system of innovative development of the industry, different to this field the entry of organizations is taken into account, these are:

- project organizations; scientific organizations engaged in construction research;
- construction of various specializations and sizes, construction-assembly organizations, construction industrial enterprises;
- transport organizations supplying construction products and construction organizations that use techniques and mechanisms;
- regional construction departments;
- manufacturer of construction materials, products and constructions enterprises;
- other organizations related to the construction sector (for example, construction equipment repair companies, suppliers of construction materials etc.).

We suggest to understand the innovative potential of construction industry enterprises as a set of production, management and organizational capabilities that provide the necessary conditions for the implementation of innovative projects. We believe that the following should be implemented in order for the factors affecting the innovative potential of construction materials industry enterprises to work more efficiently. In order to increase the intellectual potential, we believe that it is appropriate to analyze the potential of existing personnel, organize retraining of employees with low results of the analysis, increase the share of

¹ <https://sqb.uz/uz/press-center/davlat-dasturlari-ijrosi/o-zsanoatqurilishbank-qurilish-materiallari-ishlab-chiqarish-sohasida-995-million-dollarlik-loyihala/>

retraining costs, and organize the organization of attaching employees to existing professional groups by drawing up individual and comparative graphs. In this way, it is possible to increase the quality of products of construction materials industry enterprises and to increase the contribution of qualified engineers and technicians.

In order for the financial and economic potential to enable the most effective realization of the company's strategic goals and development directions, by studying the position of financing sources in the market, attracting foreign investments to increase the usefulness of innovations, issuing additional shares and bonds for a specific investment project, and giving the investor a profit share after the investment project is implemented. will be achieved through the wide involvement of equity financing of investors with the condition of transfer.

In our opinion, based on our analysis and study of the reforms carried out by foreign and domestic scientists, we believe that the following are the main factors affecting the innovative potential of construction materials industry enterprises:

- intellectual capacity
- financial and economic potential
- production - technological potential
- scientific and technical potential
- organizational - management potential
- marketing potential²

More than 1,500 projects with a total value of 5.7 billion dollars are planned to be implemented in the field of construction materials in 2022-2026 as part of the programs for the development of the industrial potential of the regions. It is noteworthy that 870 projects with a total value of 1.4 billion dollars will be launched during the reporting period, in particular, 370 million dollars were used in the previous period, of which 280 million dollars were used for foreign investment and loans.

As a result of the implementation of these projects, new types of construction materials such as cement, pipes and geogrids, ceramic granite, screw nails, marble, travertine and granite slabs, reinforced concrete, ceramic tiles, plasterboard sheets, aerated concrete and foam concrete blocks will be produced. will be done.

In particular, according to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 30, 2021 No. PQ-72 "ON THE APPROVAL OF THE INVESTMENT PROGRAM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN FOR 2022 — 2026 AND THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A NEW APPROACH AND MECHANISMS OF INVESTMENT PROJECT MANAGEMENT" According to the "Uzsanoatqurilishmateriallari" association, with the participation of foreign investments and loans, 21 projects worth 495.7 million dollars are expected to be absorbed this year by 172.7 million dollars³

² Хайдарова Э. Building materials industry enterprises factors affecting innovation capacity effective use. <https://uzresearchers.com/index.php/BTRT/article/view/755>

³ https://uzsm.uz/uz/press_center/releases/28220/

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